

Predicting Corporate Bankruptcy Using Deep Learning Algorithms

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Abstract—Predicting a company’s bankruptcy is a non-trivial task, complicated by the fact that company insolvency cases are rare, thus, unevenly distributed. In this research work, we propose a Transformer-based architecture for bankruptcy prediction using a three-year temporal window of firm-level accounting data. We train the Transformer Encoder with class-balancing, EMA-based validation, and an automated hyperparameter search, and further ensemble the models to enhance stability. Experiments on a public U.S. stock market bankruptcy dataset demonstrate state-of-the-art performance. Our ensemble achieves a test AUC of 0.903, surpassing the previous best 0.847 on the same benchmark. Notably, this improvement is attained with a shorter input window (3 years vs. 4 years), which indicates that the model captures relevant time dependencies more effectively. These results highlight the power of Transformer-based models for financial risk predictions.

Index Terms—Bankruptcy prediction, probability of bankruptcy, deep learning, Transformers, model ensembling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bankruptcy is defined as the inability of a debtor, as recognized by a court, to fully satisfy creditors’ claims arising from monetary obligations or to fulfill obligations to make mandatory payments. In the financial modeling system for assessing the probability of a company’s bankruptcy, key approaches include Altman’s two-factor and five-factor models, Taffler’s model, Lis’s discriminant model, Ohlson’s O-Score model, J. Fulmer’s model, the Davydov–Belikov models, and others [4]. However, based on recent literature, classical bankruptcy prediction models are associated with such drawbacks as sensitivity to outliers and multicollinearity arising from shared accounting components, which may reduce predictive effectiveness [8]. In contrast, machine learning techniques offer a high potential to improve predictive accuracy and adaptability when analyzing large and heterogeneous datasets.

The practical value of machine learning is evident in situations where early detection of risk incidents is required, and the volume of data make manual analysis time-consuming and labor-intensive. The computational experiment in this study focuses on a reproducible model testing on fixed data splits and on a metric resistant to class imbalance - AUC.

To deal with class imbalance and reduce the risk of overfitting, several training strategies are employed. Specifically, a weighted random sampler or a weighted loss function is applied to make sure bankruptcy cases have an adequate representation during training. The AdamW optimizer is also used

with weight decay, along with a cosine annealing learning rate schedule and an initial warm-up phase. To make evaluation more stable, model parameters are averaged using an exponential moving average (EMA). Hyperparameter optimization is conducted using Optuna, a Bayesian optimization framework. The optimized hyperparameters are then used to train the final model multiple times on a fixed set of random seeds, and an ensemble is created by averaging the predicted probabilities across these runs. In this way we see that the predictions produced are much more consistent, achieving validation AUC ≈ 0.844 and test AUC ≈ 0.903 . Further, all other evaluation metrics stated in related works are monitored to ensure the study is consistent and complete.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- We develop a Transformer encoder architecture that fits multi-year accounting data, expanding its competitiveness on time-dependent prediction tasks typically handled by recurrent models.
- We leverage automated hyperparameter optimization and ensembling to handle class imbalance and reduce training variance in bankruptcy prediction.
- We adopt a strict evaluation protocol with a temporary hold-out test set to ensure evaluations are leakage-free and performance is trusted.

II. RELATED WORKS

Lombardo et al. (2022) conducted one of the most comprehensive studies on corporate bankruptcy prediction in the American stock market [7]. In the first article “*Machine Learning for Bankruptcy Prediction in the American Stock Market: Dataset and Benchmarks*”, made in 2022, a wide range of models, such as logistic regression, SVM, Random Forest, Boosting Algorithms, and a standard artificial neural network (ANN) were trained using the same training set. The best AUC-Score of 0.893 on test data was archived by the neural network when trained on a 5-year window. Overall, Lombardo et al. concluded that neural networks should be preferred among all the ML models for the bankruptcy prediction tasks since they present the best ability to generalize on new and unseen cases. Yet, they cautioned that neural models require careful design, more computation, and multiple trials to handle training difficulty and variance.

In light of the results achieved, they critically discussed the most crucial metrics for this task as proposed benchmarks for

the future, such as: Area Under the Curve (AUC), precision, recall, type I error, type II error, and macro- and micro-F1 scores.

In the later article (2024) "A Multi-head LSTM Architecture for Bankruptcy Prediction with Time Series Accounting Data" the authors compared the multi-head LSTM, a single-input LSTM with the best traditional classifiers from their earlier benchmark [6], finding that although the Multi-head LSTM achieved the best AUC of approximately 0.84–0.85 on the 2015–2018 test period, it produced fewer false alarms. The optimal window for the LSTM models was stated to 4 years, yielding better performance than 5 years - an interesting nuance, as it suggests that including the fifth year did not help LSTM as much and could introduce noise or data sparsity issues. The investigations, made by Pellegrino, M., Lombardo, G. et al., provide an extensive basis for further research in this field.

III. DATASET OVERVIEW AND DATA PREPARATION

In this study, we use the *Bankruptcy prediction dataset for American companies in the stock market*, developed by Pellegrino, M., Lombardo, G. et al. and published on GitHub [5]. The dataset provides statistics related to the public companies in the American Stock market (New York Stock Exchange and NASDAQ). The overall accounting data covers 8,262 different companies in the period between 1999 and 2018.

The `dataset_paper.zip` file archive is unpacked, after which three table files are read: `financial_train.csv`, `financial_validation.csv`, `financial_test.csv`. Each table contains the company identifier `cik`, the fiscal year `fyear`, the status label `status_label`, and a set of numerical financial indicators, which are presented in Table I.

TABLE I: Numerical financial features used in the study

Variable name	Variable name
Current assets	Total assets
Cost of goods sold	Total long-term debt
Depreciation and amortization	EBIT
EBITDA	Gross profit
Inventory	Total current liabilities
Net income	Retained earnings
Total receivables	Total revenue
Market value	Total liabilities
Net sales	Total operating expenses

A positive aspect of the dataset’s quality is the complete time continuity of financial features. All observations have full info on current assets, total assets, cost of goods sold, and other accounting indicators. Such completeness is key for financial analysis, as it keeps time series consistent. In total, 18 base financial features are used to describe the economic condition of each company in a given fiscal year.

At the “raw” level, each sample has 57 columns, with 3 columns for `cik`, `fyear`, `status_label`, and the remaining 54 columns with prefixes `1_`, `2_`, and `3_`, which denote a feature block for the most recent year, the previous year,

and the year preceding it, respectively. The feature block was constructed by selecting only numerical financial variables, making sure that company identifiers and target labels were not included in the feature matrix. During data loading, it was noticed that the train dataset covered the period of 14 years (2001-2014), the validation dataset covered only one year (2015), and the test dataset covered 2016-2018, which did not correspond to the dataset breakdown in the related works [7] [6]. Therefore, it was decided to reassemble the dataset and divide it into three separate parts, ensuring that the validation sample covered 2012-2014 and the test sample covered 2015-2018, as in the original articles.

TABLE II: Summary of the financial dataset split

Split	Total samples	Bankrupt samples	Bankrupt rate
Train	2552	330	0.1293
Validation	590	73	0.1237
Test	3048	99	0.0325

The splits were checked for correctness based on size consistency, positive class proportions, and time indexing. The positive class was defined as bankruptcy, and the negative class as a healthy firm. Checking the distributions showed a clear imbalance, mostly in the test sample, where the amount of positive examples is much lower than in training and validation. This difference in proportions is recorded in Table II as a characteristic of the data and is considered when selecting training schemes. Due to significant imbalance we need to rely on ranking metrics such as AUC rather than accuracy.

A. Data Preprocessing

To prepare the data, we transformed our tabular data into tensor format. We did this by breaking down the feature names into two parts: the “base” (for example, `total_assets`) and the “position in window” (which ranges from 1 to 3). This allowed us to organize the numbers into tensors with the shape

$$(N, 3, 18)$$

, representing three time steps and 18 basic financial features for each step. Within each window, features are listed in order from the oldest ($t - 2$) to the most recent (t) fiscal year. The choice of a three-year history is consistent with the default bankruptcy forecasting setup based on accounting time series described in [7].

It can be stated that a window length = 3 is a compromise between informativeness and stability, since in accounting data, 1 year reflects only one-time effects, whereas 5 years provides more information but the number of available companies decreases significantly, the entry size increases (90 features), and the risk of overfitting and instability due to noise or data sparsity is higher. The three-year window is widely used as the minimum sufficient history for identifying stable signs of financial deterioration (liquidity stress, profitability decline, leverage growth). Figure 1 illustrates the overall bankruptcy

rate by fiscal year. In some periods, bankruptcy rates have been higher than usual, for example during the Great Recession between 2007-2008.

Fig. 1: Bankruptcy rate by fiscal year (2001-2018) [5]

A technical check for potential data leakage was done by separately building training, validation, and test tensors using identical feature representations, a fixed column order, and a unified label encoding scheme. Target variable $y \in \{0, 1\}$ is binary, with $y = 1$ representing a bankrupt firm (positive class), while $y = 0$ denotes a financially healthy firm (negative class). This ensures no statistical data or metadata from validation or testing was used in preparing the training data. Since the published dataset already provides features for a 3-year window, there was no need in padding input sequences in the present experiments, and firm-year observations prior to 2001 were excluded naturally, as they do not provide sufficient historical context to construct complete input sequences.

Before normalization, quantile-based clipping computed exclusively on the training split is applied to control outliers. The training tensor \mathbf{X}_{tr} is reshaped into $(N_{\text{tr}} \cdot WL, F)$, where WL is the window length and F - the number of numerical features, and each feature-related lower and upper quantiles q_{lo} and q_{hi} are estimated. In our experiments, $q_{\text{lo}} = 0.005$ and $q_{\text{hi}} = 0.995$. Values that are not in the range are clipped to the corresponding quantile thresholds. The same clipping thresholds are applied to the validation and test splits.

Numerical features are standardized by subtracting the feature-wise mean and dividing by the standard deviation, which are computed only on the training split. Formally, each feature value $X_{i,t,f}$ is transformed as

$$\tilde{X}_{i,t,f} = (X_{i,t,f} - \mu_f) / \sigma_f, \quad (1)$$

where μ_f and σ_f denote the mean and standard deviation of feature f estimated across all time steps in the training data [3]. The resulting normalization parameters (μ_f, σ_f) are reused unchanged for the validation and test splits. To guarantee numbers are stable, standard deviations below a small threshold are clipped before normalization.

Although padding is not used for a window length = 3, future experiments with variable window lengths may involve defining appropriate padding. However, in sequence-based models, a single year-index mapping is defined and used to incorporate calendar year information through trainable

embeddings. For a firm with fiscal year y , the corresponding year sequence is defined as

$$\mathbf{y}^{\text{seq}} = [y - 2, y - 1, y]. \quad (2)$$

All years appearing across the dataset are collected into a shared vocabulary and mapped to integer indices via a single global mapping. This produces a tensor

$$\mathbf{Y}_{\text{idX}} \in \mathbb{N}^{N \times WL}, \quad (3)$$

which is used to retrieve trainable year embeddings within the model.

Storing fully processed tensors \mathbf{X}_{tr} , \mathbf{X}_{va} , \mathbf{X}_{te} and corresponding year-index tensors \mathbf{Y}_{idX} after preprocessing also ensures that identical input data are used during experimental runs, eliminating unintended variations in data and reducing the risk of leakage.

IV. MODELS AND EVALUATION

A. Model Architecture and Training Protocol

The model utilized in this study represents a BERT-like Transformer Encoder without a Decoder part. Such Transformer Encoders can outperform classical time-series models on classification benchmarks [11]. Transformer Encoders for Time Series are based on a modified Transformer Encoder architecture tailored for tabular time-series data. The proposed model in this study is as follows: each training sample is represented as a multivariate time series $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{WL \times F}$ of length WL with F financial variables, where

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{WL}], \quad \mathbf{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^F.$$

Each time step vector \mathbf{x}_t is projected into a latent space of dimension d_{model} using a linear transformation [11]:

$$\mathbf{u}_t = \mathbf{W}_p \mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_p, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}} \times F}$ and $\mathbf{b}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}}$ are learnable parameters, and $\mathbf{u}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}}$ denotes the embedded representation at time step t . The resulting sequence of embeddings serves as the input to the Transformer Encoder [11].

To incorporate temporal information, two types of embeddings are added to the projected features:

- Year embeddings, which allow the model to distinguish identical financial indicators observed at different reporting periods.
- Positional embeddings, which encode the relative position of each element within the temporal window of length WL .

In addition, a learnable classification token [CLS] is added to the input sequence. The first token in each sequence is always a special classification token [CLS]. The final hidden state corresponding to this token is used as an aggregated representation of the sequence for classification tasks.

The Transformer Encoder consists of multiple stacked layers, each containing a multi-head self-attention mechanism and a position-wise feed-forward network. The self-attention mechanism enables the model to dynamically weight the

importance of different time periods and financial features when forming the final representation [10]. Each layer of the Transformer Encoder uses a pre-layer normalization (Pre-LN) configuration. This means each sub-layer is preceded by LayerNorm normalization. As for the activation function, we use GELU. Unlike such activation functions as ReLU, GELU is a smooth nonlinear function, which means it creates fewer “jagged” gradients and is regarded as a standard for BERT-like Transformers and in many cases is better for time series [2].

Figure 2 demonstrates the ability of the function to introduce smooth, probabilistic gating.

Fig. 2: GELU differs from ReLU by being smooth and non-monotonic, with a slight negative dip around $x = -0.5$ [2]

Afterwards, the output of the [CLS] token is fed into a linear classification head, producing a scalar logit. During training, the model is optimized using the binary cross-entropy loss with logits, which implicitly applies the sigmoid function. The sigmoid function maps any input value to the interval $(0, 1)$, making it possible to interpret the model’s output as a probability.

A brief training scheme can be described in Figure 3.

In short, as the classes are imbalanced, we need to implement techniques to increase the frequency of minority-class samples in training batches. In the first training run, we applied only WeightedRandomSampler, while during hyperparameter optimization, we gave the algorithm a choice between using WeightedRandomSampler, applying a weighted loss function via the `pos_weight` parameter, or even omitting imbalance handling at all. In the first variant, we give the model over-sampled bankrupt cases during the training, in the second one - assign a higher loss for misclassifying bankruptcies by adjusting the `pos_weight` coefficient.

The model parameters were optimized using the AdamW optimizer with L_2 regularization (weight decay). A cosine annealing learning rate schedule was employed, along with

a warm-up phase during the initial training epochs to archive optimization stability.

B. Exponential Moving Average of Weights

To further enhance generalization performance, an exponential moving average (EMA) of model parameters was maintained during training. The exponential moving average (EMA) is defined recursively as

$$\mathbf{x}_0^{\text{EMA}} = \mathbf{x}_0, \quad \mathbf{x}_{t+1}^{\text{EMA}} = \alpha \mathbf{x}_t^{\text{EMA}} + (1 - \alpha) \mathbf{x}_{t+1}, \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is the smoothing coefficient `ema_decay` [9].

In our task, using EMA makes sense because we have a strong class imbalance, Cosine LR, and AUC as a metric. All these are noisy updates, and EMA smooths out this noise. In Figure 3 it is seen that EMA exists in parallel with the main Transformer model and is updated by constantly averaging the main model parameters, without participating in optimization. The EMA weights, which are more stable and give better results than the raw model parameters, are used for validation performance evaluation and early stopping. The final model used for testing and inference therefore corresponds to the EMA-averaged parameters.

C. Experiments and Model Selection

TABLE III: Baseline training configuration of the Financial Transformer model

Hyperparameter	Value
Model dimension d_{model}	96
Number of attention heads n_{head}	4
Number of encoder layers num_layers	2
Feed-forward dimension dim_ff	256
Dropout rate $dropout$	0.10
Optimizer $optim$	AdamW
Learning rate lr	2×10^{-4}
Weight decay $weight_decay$	2×10^{-2}
Learning rate schedule $lr_scheduler$	Cosine annealing
Warm-up epochs $warmup_epochs$	8
Maximum number of epochs T_{max}	200
Early stopping patience $patience$	25
Training batch size $batch_size$	128
Validation batch size $batch_size$	512
Test batch size $batch_size$	512
Class imbalance handling	WeightedRandomSampler
EMA_decay $decay$	0.999

To get more reliable and computationally less expensive results, we opted for the multi-run approach for the base model configuration. Specifically, the `seed` was the only variable parameter from 1000 to 1049 across multiple model runs. At each run, the model was trained to convergence with early stopping. Using those runs, we were able to choose the model with the best val AUC and evaluate its performance on the test. It is crucial to note that the results of the test sample were not used for decision-making, which prevents data leakage and bias in quality assessment. For the base model configuration, the fixed hyperparameters are shown in Table III.

The process we performed allows us to evaluate the sensitivity of the baseline model to the variance in seeds, as

Fig. 3: Training scheme with sampling, EMA-based validation, and early stopping.

well as examine the dispersion of validation AUC scores to determine the likelihood that the final result is due to a randomly successful run.

The selection of further Transformer hyperparameters was performed using the Optuna framework with Bayesian optimization based on the Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) to learn from previous trials. This approach improves the efficiency of hyperparameter search by concentrating computational resources on promising regions of the search space and discarding poorly performing configurations early through pruning.

Each configuration was evaluated at $N_TRIALS = 70$, across several predefined seeds ($TRIAL_SEEDS = [1010, 1022, 1030, 1041, 1001]$), randomly chosen from the baseline runs. This was to ensure that the training pipeline is consistent with the base configuration while modifying hyperparameters that only impact the classification quality of the model. During optimization, Optuna averages the metric over a number of seeds and penalizes the unbalanced configurations by introducing a variance-aware objective of the form $mean - 0.25 \cdot std$, favoring stable solutions. Crucially, the test set is never used throughout optimization.

Several parameters were kept fixed during hyperparameter optimization, as summarized in Table IV.

TABLE IV: Fixed training parameters used during hyperparameter optimization: primarily control the training stability, rather than the representative performance of the model.

Parameter	Value
Train batch size	128
Validation batch size	512
Test batch size	512
Warm-up epochs	8
Maximum number of epochs	200
Early stopping patience	25

The following hyperparameters were optimized:

- hidden dimension d_{model} ;
- number of attention heads n_{head} ;
- number of Transformer Encoder layers num_layers ;
- dropout rate $dropout$;
- feed-forward dimension multiplier ff_mult ;
- learning rate lr and weight decay $weight_decay$;
- class balancing strategy;
- EMA decay factor $decay$;

The hyperparameter configuration achieving the best Optuna objective value 0.8355 was selected as the final model configuration. It is worth noting that the validation AUC derived from the hyperparameter optimization is lower than the best validation result observed in individual training runs. This behavior is expected, since the Optuna objective is defined as the average validation AUC over several random seeds, plus a penalty equal to the standard deviation of the metric. The optimal hyperparameters are summarized in Table V.

TABLE V: Best configuration selected by Optuna

Hyperparameter	Value
d_{model}	128
n_{head}	2
Number of layers	4
Dropout rate	0.15
FFN multiplier	4
Learning rate	8×10^{-4}
Weight decay	3.0×10^{-5}
Class balancing	WeightedRandomSampler
EMA decay	0.9975

Finally, we built an ensemble of models based on the Optuna configuration. We trained a specific set of models on a predefined list of random seeds $TRIAL_SEEDS = [3000, 3001, 3002, 3003, 3004, 3005]$. We set them prior to the training and did not change them after reviewing the results.

Each model was trained separately on the training sample and stopped early based on AUC on validation. EMA weights were used for evaluation, the same way as in the baseline. Moreover, at the ensemble stage, we combined the models based on their probabilities. For each company, the probability of bankruptcy was calculated by each model, and thereafter the ensemble-generated probability was determined by simple averaging. The advantage of this approach is that it smooths statistical errors; a single model may be wrong on some examples, but averaging provides a more stable ranking function. Therefore, ensemble typically enhances AUC and decreases performance sensitivity to a particular seed.

D. Evaluation Metrics

The primary evaluation metric is the area under curve, defined as:

$$AUC = \int_0^1 TPR(FPR) d(FPR), \quad (6)$$

where

$$\text{TPR} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, \quad \text{FPR} = \frac{FP}{FP + TN}. \quad (7)$$

AUC measures the model’s ability to rank positive and negative instances correctly and is independent of any specific classification threshold.

Additionally, several threshold-dependent metrics were analyzed [6]:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{F1-score} = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{\text{Precision}} + \frac{1}{\text{Recall}}} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Macro-F1} = \frac{1}{2} (\text{F1}_{\text{pos}} + \text{F1}_{\text{neg}}). \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Micro-F1} = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}. \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Type I Error} = \frac{FP}{TN + FP} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Type II Error} = \frac{FN}{TP + FN} \quad (15)$$

Equations 9, 10, and 11 report how these quantities are computed for the positive class. The definition for the negative class is exactly the same by inverting positives with negatives. In our case bankruptcy is a positive class. Because bankruptcy is a rare event, using the classification accuracy to measure a model’s performance can be misleading since it assumes that type I error (Eq 14) and type II error (Eq 15) are equally costly. Actually, the cost of false negatives is much greater than the cost of false positives for financial risk-management. In light of this, there is a need to compute and report type I and type II errors [6].

In addition, we compute Macro-F1 and Micro-F1. Macro-F1 is a stricter metric than the standard F1-score, as it gives equal weight to each class by averaging the class-wise F1 values, regardless of class frequencies. Tracking this metrics does not allow the model to “hide” behind the imbalance, achieving misleadingly high scores by favoring the majority class.

E. Threshold Selection

Practical deployment of the model requires selecting a decision threshold τ to convert predicted probabilities into binary outcomes:

$$\hat{y} = \begin{cases} 1, & \hat{p} \geq \tau, \\ 0, & \hat{p} < \tau. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Examples of changes in the interpretation of model probabilities due to different thresholds are visible in Figure 4 [12].

Fig. 4: Confusion matrices calculated on different thresholds.

Our task implies that missing a bankruptcy is much more serious than getting false alarms, so the threshold selection algorithm should increase Recall. However, if we make the model “too lenient”, there is a high probability that it will assign the True label so often that false alarms boost, making the model not valid in real business implementation. Therefore, we introduce a cost-sensitive strategy by assigning different weights to false negatives (c_{fn}) and false positives (c_{fp}). This approach allows controlling the number of missed bankruptcies while keeping the number of false alarms at an acceptable level. In general, the threshold selection process is standardized as the algorithm below 5:

Algorithm: Cost-sensitive threshold selection on the validation set

Input: validation labels y_{true} , predicted scores y_{score} , cost weights c_{fn} , c_{fp} , threshold grid grid

Output: optimal threshold thr_{star} and associated statistics info

- 1) Initialize $\text{best_cost} \leftarrow +\infty$ and $\text{thr}_{\text{star}} \leftarrow \text{None}$.
- 2) For each threshold thr in grid , compute the confusion matrix $(\text{tn}, \text{fp}, \text{fn}, \text{tp})$.
- 3) Compute the weighted misclassification cost
$$\text{cost} = c_{fn} \cdot \text{fn} + c_{fp} \cdot \text{fp}.$$
- 4) If $\text{cost} < \text{best_cost}$:
 - update best_cost , thr_{star} , and store tn , fp , fn , tp , cost , thr in info .
- 5) Return thr_{star} and info .

Fig. 5: Cost-sensitive threshold selection

The threshold is computed on the validation set only to avoid skewed results. The threshold is then fixed and applied to the test set without further adjustments. In the case of an ensemble, the threshold is selected also on the validation set based on final averaged ensemble probabilities.

We chose $c_{fn} = 30.0$ and $c_{fp} = 1.0$ to encourage higher recall for bankruptcy cases, while still penalizing for excessive false positives.

V. RESULTS

The baseline Transformer, trained on 50 different runs, exhibits a mean validation AUC of 0.8007. The majority

of values are concentrated between the range 0.82 – 0.85. 95% confidence interval [0.7903, 0.8111] indicates that even in the worst-case scenarios, the model outperforms classical machine learning algorithms [7]. The standard deviation of 0.0375 refers to the sensitivity of deep learning algorithms to stochastic factors. Depending on the random seed, the model’s performance varies significantly. This variability arises from algorithmic sources of randomness such as weight initialization, data shuffling, and optimizer behavior, which affect the trajectory of model training and lead to inconsistent outcomes [1]. These variance incentivize the use of averaging multiple runs results or ensembling. The distribution is presented in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Distribution of the AUC values on validation for the baseline Financial Transformer model.

The best-performing run achieves a validation AUC of 0.8611. The seed of this run was taken to estimate test AUC. Interestingly, the AUC of the test slightly exceeds the AUC of the validation, reaching 0.9059. However, the difference is not abnormal and may be due to more cautiously behavior of the model during validation plus EMA + early stopping. What is more, we earlier observed the difference in proportions of total and bankrupt samples between validation and test splits II, what could explain this difference. The same pattern shows up across multiple random seeds of the optimized Transformer (Table VII): the test AUC keeps scoring higher than the validation AUC, which assumes this isn’t a coincidence, but rather a systemic bias.

Even though our best single model achieves a test AUC of 0.906 and its reproducibility is close to perfect, its implementation in real-world conditions is accompanied by serious difficulties. Under the cost-sensitive thresholding scheme with $c_{FN} = 30$ and $c_{FP} = 1$, the model classifies more than half of non-bankrupt firms as bankrupt, resulting in false-positive rate 0.57, which is excessively high. This behavior is not caused by an inappropriate threshold choice, as the threshold is selected according to a predefined criterion and then fixed

Fig. 7: ROC curve on the test sample for the best baseline Financial Transformer model selected by validation AUC.

for testing. Rather, this model arose as a result of a successful random initialization taken from the tail of the validation AUC distribution.

By selecting one outstanding object based solely on AUC, as clearly shown in Table VI, we risk getting an overly optimistic view of the model’s real capabilities.

TABLE VI: Test performance of the best single-run model

Metric	Value
AUC	0.9059
Decision threshold	0.3437
True Positives (TP)	97
False Negatives (FN)	2
False Positives (FP)	1677
True Negatives (TN)	1272
Accuracy	0.4491
Precision	0.0547
Recall	0.9798
F1-score	0.1036
Macro-F1	0.3530
Micro-F1	0.4491
Type I error (FPR)	0.5687
Type II error (FNR)	0.0202
Balanced accuracy	0.7056

TABLE VII: Per-seed performance of the optimized Transformer model

Seed	Val AUC	Test AUC	Best epoch
3000	0.8295	0.8861	30
3001	0.8620	0.8674	21
3002	0.8420	0.8928	35
3003	0.8250	0.8004	54
3004	0.7846	0.8718	38
3005	0.7798	0.8958	34

In Table VII, we can see the results of our optimized Transformer model for six random seeds; the validation AUC

values range from 0.7798 to 0.8620, with an average of 0.8205 and a standard deviation of 0.0324. The model is clearly sensitive to random initialization. For the test set, the results are almost the same: AUC values range from 0.8004 to 0.8958; with an average value of 0.8690 and a standard deviation of 0.0355. This statistics confirms that relying on a single run can skew our conclusions, making them overly optimistic or pessimistic based solely on the selected seed.

Fig. 8: ROC curve on the test sample for the ensemble model.

TABLE VIII: AUC performance of the ensemble model

Split	AUC
Validation (ensemble)	0.8442
Test (ensemble)	0.9032

The ensemble ultimately outperforms the average result of any single run, achieving a validation AUC of 0.8442 and a test AUC of 0.9032. One reason for this is how ensembling reduces variance. Individual models may overfit or underfit different subsets of the data, averaging their predictions eliminates idiosyncratic errors. It also reduces the likelihood of selecting a random high-performing run, the very outlier that is at the other end of the validation AUC distribution.

As we show in Table IX, recall of the ensemble is slightly lower than that of the best single-run baseline model. However, the false positive rate is significantly decreased, and overall accuracy and Macro-F1 are significantly higher: this is undoubtedly a more suitable for real-world deployment solution. The t-SNE visualization of the ensemble predictions on the test set in Figure 9 further illustrates the behavior of the proposed model. Scattered false negatives appear next to dense clusters of healthy companies: these are cases that are inherently ambiguous, rather than systematic model failure. False positives accumulate at the boundaries of bankruptcy zones, demonstrating a cautious approach of our cost-sensitive threshold decision rule. Nothing resembling isolated pockets

TABLE IX: Test performance of the ensemble model

Metric	Value
AUC	0.9032
Decision threshold	0.4258
True Positives (TP)	79
False Negatives (FN)	20
False Positives (FP)	463
True Negatives (TN)	2486
Accuracy	0.8415
Precision	0.1458
Recall	0.7980
F1-score	0.2465
Macro-F1	0.5790
Micro-F1	0.8415
Type I error (FPR)	0.1570
Type II error (FNR)	0.2020
Balanced accuracy	0.7985

of error is observed. Overall, the ensemble paints a border that is uniform and smooth, rather than discontinuous; and this confirms why this method provides real stability along with robustness.

Fig. 9: ROC curve on the test sample for the ensemble model.

From the perspective of business, the ensemble appears to adopt a risk-averse approach. Missing a real bankruptcy will incur costs far greater than the costs of temporarily marking a stable firm as a bankrupt. By penalizing false negatives more than false positives, the ensemble focuses on spotting bankrupt firms, achieving a 79.8% success rate in bankruptcy detection. In the research study using recurrent neural networks, the maximum Recall on the test is achieved at a level of 78% [6]. The total number of missed bankruptcies is just 0.66%.

At the same time, false positives are not free either: mistakenly predicting healthy companies as bankrupt in the first place can lead to expensive financial actions, tighter capital limits, and may undermine confidence in machine-learning risk assessment systems. We managed to correctly predict the non-bankrupt companies at a rate of 84.3% so the ensemble decisions are balanced.

TABLE X: Business interpretation of ensemble test results

Category	Value	Share, %
<i>Bankrupt companies (label = 1)</i>		
Total bankrupt companies	99	
Correctly detected (TP)	79	79.80%
Missed bankruptcies (FN)	20	20.20%
<i>Non-bankrupt companies (label = 0)</i>		
Total non-bankrupt companies	2949	
Correctly classified (TN)	2486	84.30%
False alarms (FP)	463	15.70%
<i>Overall performance</i>		
Correct predictions	2565 / 3048	84.15%
False alarms (overall)	463	15.19%
Missed bankruptcies (overall)	20	0.66%
<i>Key risk metrics</i>		
Recall (bankruptcy detection)		79.80%
Precision (bankruptcy credibility)		14.58%
F1-score		24.65%

Overall, we can infer that the proposed Transformer ensemble is able to extract important temporal insights from the financial reports and creates a solid foundation for risk-oriented predictions, especially in conditions of strong class skewedness.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed a Transformer-based configuration for bankruptcy risk detection, which clearly tackles the challenges of class imbalance and training instability that often plague financial models. Using class-balancing strategies, EMA-based validation, automated optimization, and ensembling across multiple random initializations, we achieve robust results on an open dataset covering bankruptcies in the United States. Our ensemble attains a test AUC of 0.903: and achieves that with a three-year window, which means it captures key temporal cues without relying on long-term historical records. These results confirm that Transformer encoders are a dependable and powerful replacement for traditional recurrent and statistical approaches for financial risk prediction. However, Transformer-based models require a rigorous training and evaluation protocol.

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